

HOW CAN TASK-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING ENHANCE STUDENTS' COMMUNICATION?

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ABSTRACT

This paper will consider whether applying Task-based approach at HCM City University of Economics in Vietnam would enhance students' communication in English. The research has covered four terms, including 180 periods and the subjects are the same students from course 42 at University of Economics, HCM City. The majority of students are in low intermediate to intermediate level. The main course book is Business English course book- Market Leader-3rd edition- by David Cotton, David Falvey & Simon Kent (Pre-intermediate & Intermediate). After finishing every unit in the course book, the students are asked to present a real-life case study based on what they have learned. To prepare for their presentation, the students need to work in group in order to plan a project. A questionnaire and tests are used in the research to measure if the new method really works in our own context. From the outcome of the research, the Task-based approach has enhanced the students' communication ability which includes four language skills, especially the speaking skill.

Key words: Task-based language teaching, communication.

1 INTRODUCTION

From the informal interviews with the new graduates, the teachers at Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics, and the recruiters of some businesses, it is found that most students are unable to communicate effectively in English. Although some students get 550 points in the TOEIC test, they cannot pass the job interviews because of their lack of proficiency in English. One of the factors involved in this problem is that The Grammar-Translation method and the Presentation-Practice-Production approach have been applied in teaching English by most of the teachers.

It is recommended that teachers should adapt other new teaching methods such as Task-based Language Teaching or Communicative Approach in their own context. From the recent researches, Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT) is perceived as the most dominant approach in language teaching, especially in EFL context.

“The most effective way to teach a language is by engaging learners in real language use in the classroom. This is done by designing tasks – discussions, problems, games, and so on – which require learners to use the language for themselves.” (Willis & Willis, 2007: 1)

This paper will consider whether applying Task-based approach at Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics in Vietnam would enhance students' communication in English.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 What is Task-Based Language Teaching?

2.1.1 Defining language learning tasks:

According to Ellis (2003), a task is considered as a plan which is designed in detail by teachers. It can be an exercise, an assignment, a project or a presentation. However, it should be well-planned and well-organized. The meaning of a task is the most primary in communication. It must be related to students' needs, experiences and background in the real-life situations or in a real business. The integration of four skills should be included in a task because one skill cannot be reinforced without practicing the other skills. Students are engaged in a meaningful task which can help them to improve their logical and critical thinking. They actually learn through the activities needed to fulfill their work. The outcome of the process is a real product which students can use in their life or their work in the future. Moreover, a task must arouse students' interest, in other words, they feel motivated to take part in the classroom activities and they are willing to fulfill the task individually or in team.

1. A task is a workplan. 2. A task involves a primary focus on meaning. 3. A task involves real-world processes of language use. 4. A task can involve any of the four language skills. 5. A task engages cognitive processes. 6. A task has a clearly defined communicative outcome. (Ellis, 2003: 9–10)

2.2.2 Defining TBLT

As Ellis notes, 'there is no single way of doing TBLT' (2009: 224). Teachers can adapt TBLT in their own classroom. Based on their own context, teachers decide how to vary or adopt the teaching method. If the new method is applied, some changes will be made in the curriculum, the syllabus and the assessment. This will lead to the kind of activity which is assigned to students in an appropriate way. Importantly, students' abilities and performance must be measured in terms of non-linguistic outcome rather than the accuracy of language use. In this way, students are more confident to enhance their communication in English without worrying about making mistakes.

Willis (1996) suggests a framework for task-based learning as follows:

Table 1: A framework for task-based learning (Willis, 1996)

Pre-task
- Teacher introduces topic and task
Task cycle
• Task

- Students carry out the task
 - Planning
- Students plan how to report on task outcome
 - Report
- Students report back to class
 - Language focus
- Analysis – Practice

2.2 Perspectives on TBLT

Ellis (2003) and Willis & Willis (2007) are in favor of approving TBLT. They agree that it matches the theory of second language acquisition, and it also supports the findings of SLA research about the language learning process as well as perception of acquiring a second language. Moreover, it is likely that TBLT can develop students' abilities in learning a foreign language, especially improving their communication in their real life when tasks are designed in meaningful and specific contexts. Therefore, it may meet students' background and their expectations in learning a foreign language in the Vietnamese context. In this way, students have a tendency to engage in doing tasks, activities, or any projects they have to do in the classroom as well as outside the classroom. They are more motivated in learning English through doing tasks without being afraid of making mistakes.

On the contrary, they argue that learning through form-focused approaches is likely to be unsuccessful. Through Grammar - Translation and Presentation – Practice - Production, teachers believe that students can master the lessons and they are likely to apply what they have learned by rules and forms of a foreign language in order to imitate and produce the good outcome exactly and correctly. Students feel more secure if teachers follow this approach, however, they cannot reproduce the products which are supposed to occur in the real life or in the workplace. The problem is that they cannot communicate well in English after graduating from university while communication is the key to their success in the future.

However, some researchers assume that the advantages of TBLT over other approaches are still a controversial issue.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Context

The research has covered four terms, including 180 periods and the subjects are the same students from course 42 at University of Economics, HCM City. Most of the students are in low intermediate to intermediate level. The main course book is Business English course book-

Market Leader-3rd edition- by David Cotton, David Falvey& Simon Kent (Pre-intermediate & Intermediate).

Market Leader is designed for students of Business English, which consists of 12 units involved in international business. It is also an integrated course including four skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing, moreover, it has updated content and authentic resource material. Therefore, it can improve students' ability to communicate in English in business fields.

The students, who have just graduated from high school, are quite familiar with Presentation-Practice- Production. They are good at grammar and structures but they seem to be reluctant in expressing themselves in English. It is difficult for them to communicate about their daily life as well as business situations. In their future jobs, they have to deal with real problems, real-life situations which requires both the knowledge and the language about business. The classroom is the place they should experience these skills with the guidance of teachers.

In the curriculum, the course books are required for all the classes at the university. However, teachers can choose the reference books and the materials suitable for their own class. More importantly, teachers can apply any teaching methods which they find the most effective in their own context. The aim of the course is that students will be able to communicate well in English at school as well as at work.

3.2 Implementing TBLT in my own context:

At the beginning of the course, the students are informed of the purpose of the research. They know what to do and how to do the tasks in class and outside the classroom to fulfill their project. They should be given clear instructions in order to do a good case study in group after each unit.

During each term, each group is assigned to prepare for one case study based on what they have learned from each unit. They can choose any topic related to the title of the unit to make a presentation in class, so they can focus on the area they are interested in.

They should work in group to make a plan and write an outline including the topic they want to present, which main points they want to cover in their presentation, which kinds of material they need to look for to support their ideas, and how to convey their message to the whole class. It is required that the presentation should be a "real" case study or a real-life situation in a specific business context. The teacher can give them some advice about the presentation before they carry out the project if they need any assistance.

They are encouraged to collect authentic materials from different sources to make the presentation relevant to the topic, and make it more interesting to attract the audience. They can get information from the internet, newspapers, TV, and so on. In this way, their materials are updated and innovative to the audience. There is a variety of data or information and there are different kinds of activities in the presentation. Some groups extract the pictures, photos, films, music, games from the internet to illustrate their main points, while others make their own video clip to set up a situation in which they are main characters. More importantly, while presenting their issue or their case in front of the class, the students need to find ways to deal with the

problem which they may have in their own context. The negotiations or possible solutions to the problem in each case study are recommended. They are engaged in the activities in meaningful ways and they also improve all the language skills, especially speaking skill. They can combine what they learn from the unit with the material from other sources to make the case study so real and informative.

They spend time reading the information related to the topic, they also illustrate the topic by pictures, charts, a short film or a video clip and so on. After collecting the information, they should write a complete essay. In addition, they listen to some recordings or watch video clips to find the most valuable and useful to make their presentation more practical and relevant. After that, they have to report to the whole class about the topic.

After their presentation, the teacher can give them some comments on what they have done. The students are assessed mainly on meaning and fluency in English, but not accuracy. The teacher should inform the students how their tasks are assessed and measured. This will be able to motivate the students to take part in the project because they are not worried about making mistakes. They have more opportunities to practice English in the way they enjoy. The project may enhance the students' interest and meet their needs because it is related to real world activities. By this way, this kind of task can enhance their fluency and real communication in English in the real life. However, all the sources included in the presentation are required to be authentic. Therefore, they have a tendency to expose to authentic English in which four skills are integrated, which usually happens in the daily life.

To make the tasks easier for the students, the teacher can suggest some topics or give some hints so that the students have some ideas to do the project. The groups can present the topics suggested by the teacher or they can set up similar situations that the groups are interested in, however, they are encouraged to apply what they have learned in the lesson to the presentation.

4 DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Questionnaire: (See appendix)

At the end of the research, each student is distributed a questionnaire, which is designed to ask their opinions about the presentations which they have done during the course. There are some criteria listed on the questionnaire such as the improvement of four skills, the interaction, and their motivation.

About the improvement of four skills, 80% of the students agree that their language skills have been improved, especially the speaking skill (95%). While few students disagree with the improvement of other skills such as listening, reading, and writing. This indicates that the research has a good impact on the speaking skill.

About the class atmosphere, 89% of the students agree they find it more interesting and interactive. Few students disagree that the class is more interactive, but they all agree they can improve their speaking. Moreover, few find it less interesting but they also say they all feel more motivated.

All of the students accept that they feel more motivated and 91% of the students are more confident.

The result of the questionnaire shows that the research may enhance the students' communication in English, especially the speaking skill. Moreover, it can make the class atmosphere more interactive. It means that the students have more chances to interact with each other in many ways by working in groups. Last but not least, the students are more motivated in learning and practicing English, which is the key to their success in their study as well as in their future jobs.

4.2 Tests

To get more valid and reliable results from the research, the researcher compares the students' test scores of the first term with the scores of the fourth term.

The difference of progress based on the average scores of each group from Test 1 and Test 2

	Test 1 (a)	Test 2 (b)	Difference (b- a)
Group 1 (high level group)	78.3%	81.6%	3.30%
Group 2 (intermediate level group)	54.7%	64.2%	9.50%
Group 3 (low level group)	33.3%	56.0%	22.70%

From the table, we can see big differences between Test 1 and Test 2 scores of the low level group and intermediate level group, while there is a small difference between Test 1 and Test 2 scores of the high level group.

It means that the low level group make the biggest progress from the research, followed by the intermediate group, and the high level group makes the least progress of the three groups.

From the data of the questionnaire and the tests, it is indicated that the students have improved their communication in English as well as their language skills, especially the speaking skill.

5 DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

During the research, there are some other factors needed to consider such as students' learning styles, the environment and the culture of the organization.

Most of the students are willing to engage in carrying out the project assigned by the teacher. They are excited to work in group to make their presentations the most effective and interesting. The case study of each group is rather well-planned and informative. They feel more confident about their language use and their performance when speaking in front of the public. They are not afraid of making mistakes, and they just focus on conveying the meaning of their communication.

They are also motivated to choose what they want to present, how to talk and know how to work in a team.

However, there are few students who seem to be reluctant in adopting the new method. They are quite reserved and slow students and they have difficulty in the speaking ability. Therefore, the teacher should pay more attention to these students to give support to them when necessary.

Based on the teacher's observation and the students' test scores, it is found that the students have been making progress considerably in terms of presenting a topic or a case study as well as communicating more effectively in English, compared their performances from the beginning to the end of the research.

In addition, the assessments for students at the end of the term or the course should be considered and adapted to the Tasked- based approach at Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics in Vietnam.

6 CONCLUSION

From the outcome of the research, the Task-based approach has enhanced the students' communication ability which includes four language skills, especially the speaking skill. It is necessary for students to adopt this new method to improve their fluency in English. According to this approach, they have an opportunity to practice English not only in class but also outside the classroom.

The curriculum and syllabus at the university is an advantage for teachers to adopt the new method. However, teachers need to design the tasks, revise the materials, and adapt TBLT to their own teaching context based on the students' personalities and their language proficiency.

It is recommended that all the teachers should apply TBLT to their teaching at Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics to meet the students' needs and the demand of the society in Vietnam.

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APPENDIX

Questionnaire

The questionnaire is designed to ask your opinions about the case study which you present during the course.

Please tick which point you agree on for each criterion.

	Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
The presentations can help you improve the speaking skill				
The presentations can help you improve the listening skill				
The presentations can help you improve the reading skill				
The presentations can help you improve the writing skill				
The presentations are likely to make your class more interesting				
The presentations are likely to make your class more interactive				
You feel more confident when speaking in public				
You feel more motivated				